

PERSONALITY AND EARLY EFFECTS OF CAFFEINE: A DYNAMICAL SYSTEMIC MODEL

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Abstract

This paper suggests a theoretical dynamical model integrating the genetic bases of personality with the effects of drugs. The proposition is based on the data obtained from a case study about the short term effect (two hours) of caffeine.

Key words: Caffeine, molecular biology, genetic base, personality, trait, dynamics.

Resumen

Este artículo sugiere un modelo dinámico teórico que integra las bases genéticas de la personalidad con los efectos de las drogas. La propuesta está basada en los datos obtenidos en un estudio de caso sobre los efectos a corto plazo (dos horas) de una dosis única de cafeína.

Palabras clave: Cafeína, biología molecular, base genética, personalidad, rasgo, dinámica.

1. Introduction

There is scientific evidence about the genetic foundation of personality but an enough descriptive and explicative model has not yet been constructed (for a review, see Ebstein, 2006). Nevertheless, some models trying to explain the genetic foundations of the effect of drugs and addiction are appearing (for instance, Torres et al., 1999 and Chao & Nestler, 2004). Some attempts have been made in order to construct a dynamical mathematical model integrating personality and addiction that are based on the existence of a unique personality trait (Amigó et al., 2008, and Caselles et al., 2006). Such an approach seems very fruitful in order to connect the genetic base of personality with the effects of a given stimulus (a drug intake, for instance). In this paper we suggest a possible theoretical structure of a model of this kind. Our proposition is based on the empirical data obtained from a case study about the short term effects (two hours) of a single dose of caffeine.

2. Molecular biology of the effects of caffeine

Considering the four adenosine receptors that have been cloned, adenosine A_1 and A_{2A}

receptors are the most likely sites of the action of caffeine (Fredholm et al., 1999). Adenosine A_{2A} receptors are mRNA and are localized with dopamine D_2 receptors in enkephalin-expressing medium-sized spiny neurons. Also, they are co-localized with dopamine D_2 receptors in the core and shell regions of the nucleus accumbens and the tuberculum olfactorium (Svenningsson et al., 1997a). Adenosine A_1 receptors are localized in almost all brain areas (Goodman and Snyder, 1982; Fastbom et al., 1987).

The central stimulatory effect of caffeine is related with inhibition of adenosine A_1 receptors. The blockade of adenosine A_1 receptors enhances the motor effects of D_1 receptor agonists (Ferré et al., 1997). Also, it has been observed that combined dopamine and NMDA (*N*-methyl-*D*-aspartate) receptors stimulation increases the release of adenosine. The released adenosine acts on adenosine A_1 receptors and decreases the release of the excitatory neurotransmitter (Harvey and Lacey, 1997). The interaction between adenosine A_1 receptors and D_1 receptors exist in dorsal striatum and the ventral tegmental area (VTA). Such interaction shows the inhibitory effect of adenosine on the transmitter release. This effect is, in part, due to an activation of potassium

channels via adenosine A₁ receptors (Dunwiddie, 1985).

The activation of adenosine A_{2A} receptors produces a decrease of the affinity of the dopamine binding to D₂ receptors (Ferré et al., 1991). Furthermore, important synergistic effects of adenosine A_{2A} receptors are antagonism and stimulation of dopamine D₁ receptors (Pina et al., 1996; Le Moine et al., 1997).

Adenosine exerts a strong inhibitor control over locus coeruleus neurons (Regenold and Illes, 1990). Adenosine exerts also a strong inhibitor control over dorsal raphe (DR) and locus coeruleus (LC) via tuberomammillary nucleus (TMN) (Hyun et al., 2005).

Caffeine increases the turnover of several monoamine neurotransmitters, like serotonin (5-HT), dopamine and noradrenalin (Fernström and Fernström, 1984; Brickford et al., 1985; Fredholm and Jonzon, 1988; Hadfield and Milio, 1989). The values of local cerebral metabolic rate for glucose are activated after 1 mg/kg and remain increased at the higher doses (2.5-10 mg/kg) in the medial and dorsal raphe nuclei and the locus coeruleus. In addition, the activation in the shell of the nucleus accumbens occurs only at high doses of caffeine (10 mg/kg, about four or five times the average daily rate of human consumption) (Nehlig, 1999). There are as well increases in 5-HT and muscarinic and δ -opioid receptors following high doses of caffeine (Shi et al., 1993, 1994). Caffeine induces dopamine and glutamate release in the shell of the nucleus accumbens (Solinas et al., 2002).

Adenosine exerts a strong inhibitor control over ascending ACh projections to the thalamus and cortex through an action onto A₁ receptors (Rainnie et al., 1994). Adenosine modulates EEG-arousal through ACh projections to the cortex (Portas et al., 1997; Rainnie et al., 1994; Strecker et al., 2000). Spontaneous ACh release depresses tonically synaptic potentials mediated by glutamate and GABA. On the other hand, the activation of NMDA receptors may "feed-back" to reduce ACh release. This "feed-back" can be interpreted as a mechanism that could place the regulation of local ACh release under the glutamatergic afferent control (Metherate and Ashe, 1995).

The regulation of arousal by adenosine, acting onto the cell bodies of the pontine cholinergic projection nuclei, has been proposed by Rainnie et al., (1994) and Strecker et al., (2000). These neurons, through their connections with cortically projecting cholinergic neurons (Mesulam et al., 1983; Schawaber et al., 1987), work to regulate cortical activity (Aguas et al., 2002; Sarter and Bruno, 2000). Adenosine A₁ receptors are involved in the tonic inhibitor action exerted by adenosine on cholinergic neuronal activity (Rainnie et al., 1994). The cortical glutamatergic input to the striatum is excitatory and acts to modulate cholinergic and GABAergic function in this nucleus (Wood et al., 1979). Acetylcholine interacts with dopamine and glutamate to regulate striatal output. Muscarinic receptors reduce extracellular glutamate levels in the rat striatum (Rawls and McGinty, 1998).

Stimulation of NK1 receptors by substance P enhances ACh release in the dorsal striatum and this fact is consistent with the anatomical evidence of a substance P-cholinergic circuit in this region (Anderson et al., 1993).

Caffeine induces genetic expression. *C-fos* is a member of a family of immediate early genes (IEGs). Caffeine induces *c-fos* in the dorsal striatum, in both substance P and enkephalin-containing GABAergic medium-sized spiny neurons (Johansson et al., 1994). Other members of the family of immediate early genes are *c-jun* and *junB*.

High doses of caffeine (doses higher than the those required to elicit behavior stimulation) increase *c-fos* both in D₁ and D₂ expressing neurons. Other dopaminergic mechanisms are needed to explain D₁ receptor-mediated increase in IEG expression. It is possible that a part of the caffeine-induced increase in *c-fos* could be due to the elevated release of glutamate (Fredholm et al., 1999; Svenningsson et al., 1996).

Svenningsson et al. (1995) found a rapid, transient, and dose-dependent increase (25, 50 and 100 mg/kg) of *c-fos*, *c-jun* and *junB* by caffeine in the striatum, especially in the lateral part. The induction peaked after 1 hour, but persisted for 2 hours and for 4 hours in the case of *junB*. A weak induction of *c-fos* and *c-jun* were observed in nucleus accumbens, but not *junD*; and a strong induction of *junB* was also observed. They found as well an induction of

AP-1 by caffeine (100 mg/kg) in striatum which peaked 2 hours after administration and increased after 4 hours. C-Fos, c-Jun and JunB proteins are components of AP-1. There was a dose-dependent induction of preproenkephalin mRNA that peaked 4 hours after administration and was still significantly increased after 8 hours. There is some evidence about the proenkephalin gene may be a physiological target for Fos and Jun in the hippocampus. Fos-Jun complexes bound specifically to a regulatory sequence in the 5' control region of the proenkephalin gene (Sonnenberg et al., 1989).

On the base of the previous cited scientific evidence, we propose a simple model of the caffeine genetic expression in two phases:

- 1) Interactions between A₁, D₁ and NMDA, in a short-term, induce genes like c-fos and c-Fos, and produce positive mood, peaked as euphoric mood.

Neurotensin and substance P neuropeptides are affected by caffeine (Schiffman & Vanderhaegen, 1993a). Both neuropeptides depend on a rise in c-Fos (Svenningsson et al., 1997b). Caffeine at high dose (75 mg/kg) induces a significant increase in the number of Fos-immunoreactive neurons in many nuclei across the entire brain (Bennett & Semba, 1998). Glutamatergic transmission via NMDA receptor contributes to the induction of substance P. Glutamate and Ach regulates substance P and enkephalin gene expression in the same direction (Somers and Beckstead, 1990; Pollack and Wooten, 1992).

Substance P increases dopamine level acting in VTA (Stinus et al., 1978) and NAC (Kombian et al., 2003).

- 2) The inhibitor effect on transmitter release as a homeostatic regulatory factor.

The activation of adenosine A_{2A} receptors increases GABA release from pallid slices (Mayfield et al., 1993). Adenosine activates gene expression of striatal enkephalinergic neurons (Karcz-Kubicha et al., 2006). The mRNA for dynorphin and enkephalin is elevated in the striatum by high doses of caffeine (Svenningsson et al., 1997). Chronic treatment with caffeine causes increased levels of preproenkephalin mRNA (Schiffmann and Vanderhaegen, 1993b).

Both enkephalin mRNA and substance P mRNA expression in the rat striatum appear tonically stimulated through postsynaptic NMDA receptor mediated mechanisms (Jolkkonen et al, 1995).

D1 receptor stimulation increases cAMP that activates protein kinase, which phosphorylates the transcription factor cAMP response element-binding protein (CREB). Phosphorylated CREB initiates transcription of IEGs. Target genes are prodynorphin and preproenkephalin (Svenningsson et al., 1997). Dynorphin binds to the κ opioid receptors on VTA dopamine cell bodies and terminals to inhibit their activity and decreases dopamine release in the NAC (Spanagel et al., 1992). Another mechanism might involve striatal dynorphin acting to reduce corticostriatal input. Findings from studies of the hippocampus indicate that dynorphin may be released by dentate granule cells to presynaptically reduce glutamate input from the cortex to the dentate gyrus (Wagner et al., 1992). With respect to cocaine, after a single injection, both c-fos and substance P mRNA levels are elevated within 30 min, whereas the elevation of dynorphin mRNA levels are delayed, which reflex a compensatory response of the dynorphin in striatonigral neurons to regulate the responsiveness of dopamine neurons (Steiner and Gerfen, 1993). On the other hand, preproencephaline mRNA increase might have an inhibitor effect, and delays the elevation level. A subpopulation of striatal neurons expresses high levels of enkephalin and D2 dopamine receptors, and projects indirectly to the midbrain via the globus pallidus and subthalamic nucleus. The activation of this indirect pathway decreases locomotion and wheel running in rats (Werme et al., 2002). Adenosine, via A_{2A} receptor increases the striatal expression of c-fos and preproenkephalin (Karcz-Kubicha et al., 2006).

3. Sensitization and tolerance

The sensitization and tolerance to some effects of the administration of repeated caffeine doses have been demonstrated in animals, but the data are less conclusive in humans. In rats, continuous oral intake or daily high dose of caffeine administration induces tolerance to caffeine motor stimulant effects (Casas et al.,

1999; Garret and Holtzman, 1995; Holtzman and Finn, 1988). In contrast, intermittent caffeine low doses administration induces sensitization (Cauli et al., 2003).

In humans, tolerance has been demonstrated for the effect of caffeine on blood pressure, heart rate, diuresis, plasma adrenaline and noradrenalin levels, and rennin activity. Tolerance has also been described in some subjective effects like anxiety, tension, jitteriness, nervousness and activity, stimulation or energy, but not alertness and wakefulness. Neither the cerebral energy metabolism has showed tolerance to caffeine (Nehlig, 1999; for a review).

4. Caffeine and mood

There is evidence that low doses of caffeine (75-150 mg) induce positive subjective effects, even in absence of acute withdrawal effects, in habitual users and habitual non-users of caffeine (Haskell et al., 2005). The administration of high (but not low) doses of caffeine increases the measures of anxiety (Stern et al., 1989).

Childs & de Wit (2006) found that acute doses of caffeine, at levels typically found in a cup of coffee, produce stimulant-like subjective effects. This study investigated the physiological, subjective and behavioral effects of 0, 50, 150, and 450 mg of caffeine. The subjects completed the subjective effects questionnaires before forty minutes after the capsules were ingested, corresponding to the approximate time that plasma peak levels of caffeine are reached for (Mumford et al, 1996). The stimulant-like subjective effects were dose-dependent. The 150 and 450 mg doses increase ratings on the A (amphetamine) scale and LSD (dysphoria) scale and decreased PCAG (sedation) scores in the ARCI (Addiction Research Centre Inventory). Caffeine increased also the ratings of "feel drug" and "drug high" (significant effects were seen with the 450 mg dose), but not of "like drug" and "want more". Caffeine also increased ratings of "anxiety", "vigor", "arousal", "positive mood", "high" and "stimulation", and significantly reduced ratings of "fatigue". Caffeine appeared to mimic the effects of amphetamines and cocaine only at rather high doses (10 mg/kg) at which binding to adenosine A₁ receptors is likely (Nehlig,

1999). Caffeine has widespread effects on the cerebral functional activity in contrast to the specific effects of amphetamine and cocaine. These substances increase the rates of cerebral glucose utilization, primarily in the shell and not in the core of the nucleus accumbens at rather low doses (Fredholm et al., 1999, for a review). Caffeine primary acts on the strapyramidal motor system and on the structures related to the sleep-wake cycle such as the reticular formation, raphe nuclei, and locus coeruleus (Nehlig et al., 1984, 1986). The cerebral energy metabolism of these structures remains increased even 5 to 6 hours after the last chronic i.p. administration of caffeine.

With respect to the effects of caffeine on performance, the dose-response curve is inverted U shaped, with doses of 500 mg causing a decrease in performance although lower doses have positive effects (Kaplan et al., 1997).

5. Case study

Two adult subjects participated in the experiment. They were male students of the Polytechnic University of Valencia (Spain), with an age of 28 and 29 years, respectively.

a) Instruments.

1. List of 12 adjectives from the Sensation Seeking Scale, selected from the MAACL by Zuckerman & Lubin (1965).
2. List of 25 adjectives of personality (Brody and Ehrlichman, 1998).

Two versions were used for the list of adjectives from the Sensation Seeking Scale: trait-format, SSS-T, ("Are you like this in general?") and state-format, SSS-S ("Are you like this at this moment?" or "do you feel so at this moment?").

The sensation seeking is considered in this study as a good approximation to the unique personality trait.

From the list of 25 adjectives of personality, the scores on three personality traits were obtained: Extraversion (E), Neuroticism (N) and Psychoticism (P).

b) Procedure

Non consumption of caffeine was required for the subjects since the last afternoon before the experiment, and that they were on fast. Once in the room where the experiment took place, they filled in two forms with the two lists of adjectives from MAACL, in trait-format and in state-format. Next, they drank two cups of coffee, with an amount of 328 mg of caffeine (280cc with a concentration of: 1172 ± 15 mg/litre). The analysis of this concentration was made in the Department of Analytical Chemistry, University of Valencia, Spain. From this moment, and during two hours, they filled in a form with the two lists of adjectives in state-format (SSS-S) each four and a half minutes, until a total of 30 registers.

6. Unique Personality Trait Theory (UPTT)

The Unique Personality Trait Theory (UPTT) (Amigó, 2005; Amigó et al., 2008) proposes an integration of all the factors above considered: biochemical and genetic effects of drugs and personality, the effects on mood, and also the sensitization and habituation mechanisms. In this study, we consider only the caffeine effects of a single dose. The UPTT proposes a hierarchical model where the highest level corresponds to the unique trait, extended from an impulsivity and aggressivity pole (approach tendency) to an anxiety and introversion pole (avoidance tendency).

7. Results and discussion

The results of the experiment are presented in Figures 1-1 to 1-3 for Case 1, and Figures 2-1 to 2-3, for Case 2. The scores in the SSS scales are:

	SSS-T	SSS-S
CASE 1	25	19
CASE 2	50	6

In Figures 1-1 and 2-1, the evolution of the scores of the unique trait of personality along the two hours can be observed. These scores represent the general activation of brain,

measured in the hedonic scale. Figures 1-2 and 2-2 represent the evolution of Extraversion, Neuroticism and Psychoticism. Figures 1-3 and 2-3 provide the evolution of the well-being and the subjective effect of coffee.

Figure 1-1: Evolution of the unique trait of personality for Case 1.

Figure 1-2: Evolution of the Extraversion, Neuroticism and Psychoticism for Case 1.

Figure 1-3: Evolution of the well-being and the subjective effect of coffee for Case 1.

Figure 2-1: Evolution of the unique trait of personality for Case 2.

Figure 2-2: Evolution of the Extraversion, Neuroticism and Psychoticism for Case 2.

Figure 2-3: Evolution of the well-being and the subjective effect of the coffee for Case 2.

Observe in Figures corresponding to Case 1 that, at minute 99 (point 22), a simultaneous recovering of the general activation and the

subjective sensation of well-being is produced. On the other hand, the evolution pattern of E, N and P is very interesting. Extraversion (E) shows an inverted U shape up to the same instant (minute 99); similarly Neuroticism (N), although its level is situated below the level of E. Psychoticism (P) shows an inverted U shape up to minute 108 (point 24), where it decreases. This P decrease coincides with the E and N recovering. Thus, the combination of high P and low E and N (between minutes 99 and 112.5) is the responsible of a lower sensation of well-being.

In Figures corresponding to Case 2, a tendency to an inverted U shape for the unique personality trait is observed, but still far to be completed. E also shows a tendency to an inverted U shape, while N tends to increase and P presents a U shape. The high N and P together with the low E coincide with the lowest levels of subjective well-being.

How can these outcomes be interpreted?

Considering the ideas exposed in the first part of this paper, we can deduce that the evolution patterns of the different personality traits are a consequence of an increase of glutamate and dopamine. This extracellular increase of the excitatory neurotransmission induces the early genes belonging the Fos family and the CREB phosphorylation. The synthesis of substance P increases the extracellular dopamine and, plausibly, contributes to the euphoric sensation produced by coffee.

The rise of subjective well-being coincides with the rise of E and N, while the reduction of subjective well-being coincides with the rise of P. It can signify that P (related with aggressiveness) represents a very high increase of dopamine level, which produces a negative hedonic tone, of aggressive kind and neither sociable nor euphoric.

But, when the inhibition mechanism takes place?

The fact that the inhibition mechanism has started inside the experimental period is clear, however, its effects have not been observed yet. The CREB phosphorylation, as remarked above, activates the prodinorfine and preproencefaline genes, which reduce the extracellular dopamine. Nevertheless, the delay of activation of this genes respect to other genes such as c-fos or

preprotachykinin A (P substance) must be taken into account.

A prolongation of the coffee effects for several hours more would be expected; nevertheless, individuals do not consider to be under this effects. During this period the inhibitor mechanism would produce a depressor effect and a hard subjective discomfort. The two cases confirm this claim. The individual of Case 2 finished the experiment with a hard excitation, and the individual of Case 1 confessed some days later that he felt an intensive depression during several hours after the experiment. This feeling was not registered. In fact, Figure 1-3 shows how, by ending the two hours of the experiment, the subject improved his well-being. But, after a short time, he felt a significant depression that can be attributed to a dopaminergic depletion produced by the action of peptides.

Does personality influence caffeine response?

The observed evolution of the SSS-S scores for Case 2 points out that the inhibitor effect has not been arisen yet given that the subject has a high excitation level when the experiment ends. The inhibitor effect in Case 1 has already arisen because his positive hedonic tone has been reduced, and even the initial hedonic tone has been recovered.

These outcomes are consistent with the SSS scores. Thus, Case 1 presents a lower trait (SSS-T = 25) than Case 2 (SSS-T = 50) and it is expected that in Case 1 the inhibitor effect arises before and reduces the positive hedonic tone. As it has been remarked above, the inhibitor mechanism has not been shown yet in Case 2. Moreover, there is a notable difference between SSS-T and SSS-S in Case 2 (44) respect to Case 1 (6). A higher phasic reaction would be expected in Case 2 and so it was.

8. Genetic dynamic model of personality and caffeine effects

From the empirical data and the theoretical review provided in this study, a dynamical model relating personality and drug effects, especially caffeine effects, seem possible to construct. It is a model of peptidic gene expression induction. Figure 3 shows its causal diagram which causal relations have been explained in this text. So, the excitation effect

power is represented by preprotachykinin, the inhibition effect power by predynorphin, while dynorphin expresses itself with delay. The homeostatic control depends on the compensatory effects to dopamine depletion (preproenkephalin).

Compensatory responses include increased synthesis of TH (tyrosine hydroxylase), increased DA release and turnover, and decreased DA uptake, leading to maintenance of normal or near normal levels of extracellular dopamine (Zhang et al., 1988; Zigmond et al., 1989, 1990; Abercrombie et al., 1990; Robinson et al., 1990; Robinson et al., 1994). Loss of dopaminergic afferents to the striatum leads to increased activity in striatal efferents to the external segment of the globus pallidus. This pathway utilizes both GABA and enkephalin as co-transmitters. Overactive enkephalinergic transmission appears to act to reduce the effects of increased GABAergic transmission (Manuef et al., 1994). Enkephalin serves to reduce GABA release in the GP and may therefore act as an adaptive mechanism, maintaining the inhibitor function of the GP in basal ganglia circuitry (Stanford and Cooper, 1999). Opioid peptides, either dynorphins acting on opioid receptors or enkephalins acting on μ -opioid receptors, exert tonic inhibition on dopamine and dynorphin B release in both substantia nigra and neostriatum (You et al., 1999).

One of the most consistent striatal responses to decreased dopamine levels is the up regulation of PPE mRNA (Tang et al., 1983; Normand et al., 1988; Augood et al., 1989; Gerfen et al., 1991). PPE mRNA expression may be an indirect indicator of dopamine function.

Figure 3. Causal diagram of caffeine genetic model. A: Adenosine; D: Dopamine; GLU: Glutamate; PPK: Preprotachynin; PPD: Preprodinorfine; PPE: Preproenkehalin.

The system shows activation and inhibitor actions. Intranigral injections of GABA or dynorphin-A inhibit, while intranigral injections of substance P or neurokinin-A stimulate dopamine levels in the ipsilateral striatum. Intranigral GABA, dynorphin-A, substance P and neurokinin-A modulation of ipsilateral striatal dopamine release is mediated via direct action on the nigrostriatal projection. Thus, it is suggested that the striatonigral pathway, which contains GABA, dynorphin, substance P and neurokinin-A, exerts a direct regulatory effect on the activity of the nigrostriatal dopamine projection (Reid et al., 1990).

This is a very simplified model. In future developments the model needs to be translated into differential equations and validated with more extensive experiments as well as disaggregated by considering more regulatory mechanisms. For instance, due to the caffeine dose is relatively high, it is possible that other inhibitor mechanisms enter into action. In addition, caffeine increases the state of phosphorylation of DARPP-32 (dopamine- and cyclic AMP-regulated phosphoprotein of relative molecular mass 32,000) at Thr 75, through inhibition of dephosphorylation rather stimulation through cyclin-dependent kinase 5 (Cdk5)-catalysed phosphorylation, of this residue (Lindskog et al., 2002). Increased phosphorylation of DARPP-32 at Thr 75 results in attenuation of dopamine signaling (Bibb, 2003). DARPP-32 is a potent inhibitor of PP-1 when phosphorylated by PKA at Thr 34. PP-1 is a serine/threonine protein phosphatase that negatively regulates the transcription of c-fos mRNA (Hagiwara et al., 1992; Liu & Graybiel, 1996). Furthermore, it is possible that DARPP-32 phosphorylates the unstable 33-kDa of $\Delta FosB$ to convert into the stable 35-to-37-kDa isoforms (Nestler et al., 2001). $\Delta FosB$ functions as a transcriptional inhibitor. Between the target genes for $\Delta FosB$ are: AMPA glutamate receptor, gene encoding dynorphin, and the Cdk5 (cyclin-dependent kinase-5) (Nestler et al., 2001). Cdk5 increase phosphorylation of DARPP-32 which is converted from an inhibitor of PP-1 to an inhibitor of protein kinase A, increasing dephosphorylation of DARPP-32 at Thr 34, and reducing the dopamine signaling.

As we explained above, the base of the Unique Personality Trait Theory (UPTT) (Amigó,

2005; Amigó et al., 2008) proposes a hierarchical model where the highest level corresponds to the unique trait, extended from an impulsivity and aggressivity pole (approach tendency) to an anxiety and introversion pole (avoidance tendency). From the suggested dynamic model, forecasting about the genetic foundation of personality is possible. Persons with a lofty score in the unique trait would have a high excitation power (low tonic level of the family of Fos genes) and, thus, they would have an great capacity of phasic response to stimulant drugs. They would have, as well, a high homeostatic control, which will allow them to recover quickly their base line. Persons with a low level of the unique trait would have a high inhibitor power (high tonic level of CREB and dynorphin) which will allow them a weak phasic reaction to the same drugs. Besides, they would have a lower homeostatic control, delaying more their base-line recovering. It has been observed that human cocaine addicts show persistent elevation of dynorphin mRNA in the caudate (Hurd and Herkenham, 1993). Over expression of CREB and dynorphin in the nucleus accumbens of rats produce depressant-like effects (Newton et al., 2002). Depression-like state mediated by CREB is defined as a general state of emotional numbness and anhedonia (Barrot et al., 2002). On the other hand, it has been found an association between the prodynorphin gene promoter polymorphism and opioid dependence (Ray et al., 2005). A review on the role of CREB in the psychopathology (addiction, depression and anxiety) is in the work of Carlezon et al., (2005).

Other experiments are needed to support the time patterns of genetic expression caused by the caffeine long term effects (4-6 hours and repeated doses). However, the two cases presented in this study are helpful for the understanding of the underlying genetic mechanisms explaining personality and their changes as a consequence of a single drug dose consumption. The suggested model relating personality and coffee effects, although still tentative and plain, tries to open a way of integration of behavior and brain functions. Thus, it merits to be developed in future research.

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